

Benzothiazole Derivatives—Part VI. Synthesis of Some 2-[2-Amino (or substituted amino)-5-ethoxycarbonyl-4-thiazolyl]-benzothiazoles as Potential Antiinflammatory Agents

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Manuscript received 29 January 1975; accepted 12 May 1975

Ten 2-[2-amino (or substituted amino)-5-ethoxycarbonyl-4-thiazolyl] benzothiazoles have been synthesised by the condensation of ethyl 2-benzothiazoloyl bromoacetate with various thioureas with a view to testing their anti-inflammatory activity. Ethyl 2-benzothiazoloyl bromoacetate was prepared by the Claisen condensation of 2-ethoxycarbonyl benzothiazole and ethyl acetate followed by bromination of the ketoester.

RECENTLY, a great deal of interest has been observed in the field of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory agents¹. In our previous papers², we have described the synthesis and antiinflammatory activity of 2- and 6-(4-thiazolyl)-benzothiazoles and 2-(2-amino-4-thiazolyl)benzothiazoles and their derivatives. These compounds were relatively non-toxic and some of them possessed antiinflammatory activity approaching that of phenylbutazone. It was therefore, considered worthwhile to develop these types of compounds further taking 2-(2-amino-4-thiazolyl)benzothiazole, which showed the highest activity and least toxicity, as the lead compound. We now report the synthesis of a number of 2-[2-amino (or substituted amino)-5-ethoxycarbonyl-4-thiazolyl]benzothiazoles (I) for the purpose of evaluation of their antiinflammatory activity.

(I)
R = H, Alkyl or Aryl

The compounds in this series have been prepared according to the following reaction scheme :

1. $\text{CH}_3\text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5$; $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{ONa}$ in C_6H_6 .
2. Br_2 in CHCl_3 .
3. RNHCSNH_2 in $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$.

Ethyl 2-benzothiazoloyl acetate (III) was prepared by the Claisen condensation of 2-ethoxycarbonyl benzothiazole (II) and ethyl acetate in the presence of sodium ethoxide in benzene. The structure of the β -keto ester (III) was confirmed by its spectral data as well as by its acidic hydrolysis to 2-benzothiazoloyl methyl ketone². Bromination of III in chloroform yielded ethyl 2-benzothiazoloyl bromoacetate (IV) in good yield. The bromo compound (IV) was then condensed with appropriate thioureas in ethanol to get the required compound I. α -Bromo- β -ketoesters are known to react with thioamides and thioureas to give thiazole-5-carboxylic esters³. The structures of the final compounds as well as the intermediates were confirmed by elemental analysis and I.R. and N.M.R. spectra wherever necessary.

Preliminary pharmacological screening⁴ of some selected compounds have shown that, in general, these compounds (I) are more toxic and less active as antiinflammatory agents than their analogues in which the carboxy group is absent².

Experimental

All the melting points were taken in open capillary in liquid bath and are uncorrected. I.R. spectra were taken on Beckman IR-20 Spectrophotometer. N.M.R. spectra were recorded on a 100 MHz Spectrometer and are expressed on the δ scale.

Ethyl 2-benzothiazoloyl acetate (III): Absolute ethanol (8.6 ml, 0.15 mole) was added dropwise to sodium sand (prepared from 3.5 g, 0.15 g atom of the metal) in dry benzene (150 ml) at such a rate so as to promote gentle refluxing until all the sodium had reacted. A solution of 2-ethoxycarbonylbenzothiazole⁵ (20.7 g, 0.1 mole) and dry ethyl acetate (17.6 g, 0.2 mole) in dry benzene (100 ml) was added slowly at room temperature with continuous stirring and the stirring continued for 8 hr. The thick sludge thus obtained was filtered, dissolved in water, treated

with an excess of acetic acid, and the liberated ester extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was washed with dilute sodium carbonate solution and then with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and ether removed. It was crystallised from pet. ether ($60^\circ\text{--}80^\circ$), m.p. 78° , yield 16 g (66%). IR (nujol), cm^{-1} : 1700 (C=O), 1735 (COOC_2H_5). NMR (CDCl_3); δ 1.3 (triplet, 3, CH_2CH_3); δ 4.2 (quartet, 2, CH_2CH_3), δ 4.3 (singlet, 2, CH_2CO); δ 7.4–8.2 (multiplet, 4, aromatic). A small signal (singlet) at δ 6.3 indicates the presence of some enol form. (Found: C, 58.12; H, 4.50; N, 5.24; S, 12.62. Calc. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{11}\text{NSO}_3$: C, 57.82; H, 4.42; N, 5.62; S, 12.85%.)

The β -keto ester (III, 1 g) was heated with 40% sulphuric acid (10 ml) on a water bath for 30 min. The solution on dilution with water gave 2-benzothiazolyl methyl ketone which crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 110° (lit.² m.p. $110^\circ\text{--}111^\circ$).

Ethyl (2-benzothiazolyl bromoacetate (IV)): To a boiling solution of III (14.94 g, 0.6 mole) in dry chloroform (100 ml) was added bromine (9.6 g, 0.6 mole) in chloroform (50 ml) dropwise and with stirring. A light yellow solid began to separate when the addition was half over. The reaction mixture was refluxed till almost all the solid had dissolved and HBr ceased to evolve. After the removal of undissolved material, chloroform was distilled off from the filtrate and the residual solid crystallised from pet. ether ($60^\circ\text{--}80^\circ$), m.p. 82° , yield 12.2 g (65%). IR (nujol) cm^{-1} : 1710 (C=O), 1735 (COOC_2H_5). NMR (CDCl_3); δ 1.3 (triplet, 3, CH_2CH_3); δ 4.3 (quartet, 2, CH_2CH_3); δ 6.2 (singlet, 1, CHBrCO); δ 7.5–8.3 (multiplet, 4, aromatic). (Found: S, 9.26; Br, 24.12; Calc. for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{10}\text{BrNSO}_3$, S, 9.75; Br, 24.39%.)

2-[2-Amino (or substituted amino)-5-ethoxycarbonyl-4-thiazolyl]benzothiazoles (I): Mono substituted thioureas were prepared according to the literature method⁶. A typical preparation of the compounds in this series is given below:

2-(2-*p*-Toluidino-5-ethoxycarbonyl-4-thiazolyl) benzothiazole (I, R = 4- $\text{HC}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$): A solution of ethyl 2-benzothiazolyl bromoacetate (IV, 5 g, 0.015 mole) in alcohol (50 ml) was mixed with a solution of *p*-tolylthiourea (2.5 g, 0.015 mole) and the mixture refluxed for 2 hr. The crystalline solid which separated on cooling was filtered, washed with a little alcohol and treated with aqueous ammonia. The solid product was collected, washed with water, dried and crystallised from toluene, m.p. 187° , yield 4 g (67%). IR (nujol) cm^{-1} : 3300 (NH), 1710 (COOC_2H_5). NMR (CDCl_3); δ 1.2 (triplet, 3, CH_2CH_3), δ 2.2 (singlet, 3, $\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$), δ 4.3 (quartet, 2, CH_2CH_3), δ 7.0–8.2 (multiplet, 8, aromatic), δ 9.2 (broad, 1, NH). (Found: C, 59.9; H, 3.66. Calc. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2\text{O}_2$; C, 60.23; H, 3.82%). The compounds thus prepared have been listed in Table 1 together with their physical and analytical data.

Acknowledgements

The authors are thankful to the authorities of Kurukshetra University for the award of a research scholarship to one of them (O.P.B.), to Prof. S. M. Mukherji, Head of the Department of Chemistry, for providing the facilities. Our thanks are also due to the Secretary, P and D Research Committee, C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the biological testing of the compounds.

TABLE 1. 2-[2-AMINO (OR SUBSTITUTED AMINO)-5-ETHOXY CARBONYL-4-THIAZOLYL]BENZOTHAZOLES (I)

Sr. No.	R	Solvent of Crystallisation	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analytical Data				IR cm^{-1} (nujol) NH	COOC_2H_5
						Found %		Required %			
						S	N	S	N		
1.	H	Benzene	152	56	$\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2\text{O}_2$	20.62	14.14	20.98	13.77	3300*	1710
2.	Ethyl	Alcohol	221	60	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2\text{O}_2$	19.04	12.99	19.22	12.61	3300	1700
3.	Allyl	Alcohol/Water	204	52	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2\text{O}_2$	18.32	11.70	18.55	12.17	3300	1710
4.	Phenyl	Benzene	221	58	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2\text{O}_2$	16.48	10.72	16.79	11.03	3300	1710
5.	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	Dioxane	226	77	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{14}\text{ClN}_3\text{S}_2\text{O}_2$	15.25	10.47	15.40	10.11	3310	1700
6.	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	Xylene	239	70	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{14}\text{ClN}_3\text{S}_2\text{O}_2$	15.20	10.02	15.40	10.11	3310	1700
7.	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	Alcohol	166	63	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2\text{O}_2$	16.53	10.14	16.20	10.63	3300	1705
8.	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	Toluene	187	67	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2\text{O}_2$	16.45	10.37	16.20	10.63	3300	1710
9.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	Xylene	231	61	$\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{S}_2\text{O}_2$	15.12	9.78	15.57	10.22	3300	1700
10.	<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	DMF	300	65	$\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{14}\text{BrN}_3\text{S}_2\text{O}_2$	14.20	9.55	13.91	9.13	3300	1700

* NH_2

References

1. W. E. COYNE in "Medicinal Chemistry", (Ed.) A. Burger, Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1970, Vol. 2, p. 953. "Annual Reports in Medicinal Chemistry", (Ed.) C. K. Cain, Academic Press, New York, 1969, p. 207. H. J. Sanders, *Chem. & Engg. News*, 1968, 46, 46.
2. S. N. SAWHNEY and J. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, 8, 882.
S. N. SAWHNEY, J. SINGH and O. P. BANSAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 566.
3. J. M. SPRAGUE and A. H. LAND, in "Heterocyclic Compounds", (Ed.) R. C. Elderfield, John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1957, Vol. 5, p. 624.
4. C. V. WINTER, E. A. RISELY and G. W. NUSS, *Proc. Soc. Exp. Biol. Med.*, 1962, 111, 544.
5. E. CAMPAIGNE and J. E. VAN VERTH, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1958, 23, 1344.
6. E. E. REID, "Organic Chemistry of Bivalent Sulphur", Chemical Publishing Co., New York, 1963, Vo. 5, p. 66.